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Designating of intelligence model needed for leadership effectiveness of sport Managers

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Abstract: Studies have shown it is essential for organizational successful to have leadership effectiveness. This is true to all organizations as sport organizations. Hence, it is important to identification of factors that can be related to leadership effectiveness. Therefore, the purpose of this research was designated of intelligence model needed for leadership effectiveness of sport managers. The Statistical popularly was all managers (N1=331) and staffs (N2=1621) of Sport and Young's Ministry, National Olympic committee, National Paralympics committee, National Olympic Academy, and Sport Federations. Based on Morgan table, 180 managers and 367 staffs were selected with stratified sampling and random sampling to this research. Shring (1998) emotional intelligence questionnaire, Van Dyne and Ang (2004) Four Factor cultural intelligence scale questionnaire, Albrecht (2002) organizational intelligence questionnaire and Leadership effectiveness questionnaire (1388) was used to collect data. Validity of the Questionnaires was confirmed by experts and the reliability coefficient for the emotional intelligence questionnaire ($\alpha=0/80$), cultural intelligence ($\alpha =0/89$), organizational intelligence ($\alpha =0/88$) and for leadership effectiveness questionnaire obtained ($\alpha=0/90$). Data analysis was performed by multiple regressions. Also, Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) was performed with AMOS graphic/18 for modeling. The results showed there was significant relationship between emotional intelligence, cultural intelligence and organizational intelligence with Leadership effectiveness. Finally, with regard to these results, it is proposed that notice to emotional intelligence, organizational intelligence and cultural intelligence in selecting of sport managers.

Keywords: Intelligence, Leadership, Sport, Effectiveness, Manager

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